

A MIXED METHOD STUDY OF TEEN PREGNANCY IN LIPA CITY

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ABSTRACT

Teen pregnancy has been a worldwide enigma for both developing and developed countries. The principal objectives of the study are as follows: 1. determine the difference between the assessment of teachers and students in the integration of sex education in the curriculum; 2. determine the relationship between the integration of sex education in the curriculum and the factors that influence teen pregnancy and; 3. create a teen pregnancy awareness program based on the result of the study. The mixed method analysis was employed in the study using the explanatory sequential approach. The study revealed a notable significant difference to the assessment of teachers and students in the integration of sex education in EsP and MAPEH. It was also disclosed the highly significant relationships between family and social factors with the integration of sex education in the curriculum. In conclusion, teen pregnancy is influenced by different factors, namely: individual, family and social factors.

Keywords: Gender and Development, teen pregnancy, demographic profile, integration of sex education research design, locale, population and sampling, instrumentation, data gathering, statistical treatment